

Karol Szymanowski:

Bridging Romanticism and Modernism in Polish Art Music

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Karol Szymanowski (1882–1937) was a transformative figure in Polish music, bridging the Romantic traditions of Chopin with the emerging 20th-century musical styles. Born in the Russian Empire to a family of Polish nobility, Szymanowski overcame personal and political challenges to become one of Poland's most celebrated composers. His work encompassed many forms, from symphonies and operas to piano miniatures and Polish folk-inspired compositions. Influenced by European masters like Strauss, Scriabin, and Debussy, Szymanowski infused his music with Impressionist colors, exoticism, and, later, a distinctively Polish idiom shaped by the folk traditions of the Tatra mountains. Despite suffering from financial hardship and ill health later in life, Szymanowski's legacy includes over 250 works, his leadership as director of the Warsaw Conservatory, and his enduring influence on 20th-century Polish music. Honored posthumously for his contributions, he remains a cornerstone of Poland's cultural and musical identity.

Early Life

Karol Maciej Szymanowski was a Polish pianist and composer born in the village of Tymoszkówka, in the Kiev Governorate region of the Russian Empire (what is now Timoshovka, Cherkasy Oblast, Ukraine) on October 6th, 1882.¹ He was a citizen of a non-existing Poland and a subject of Czar Nicholas II – born to the wealthy Korwin-Szymanowski family of the Polish gentry class: a legally privileged noble class within the Grand Duchy of Lithuania and the Kingdom of Poland (also known as the *szlachta*).² Szymanowski had been a normal school student originally, but a leg injury led to an inability to attend school, and instead, schoolwork was replaced with diligent music studies. His initial studies were done privately through his father until his enrollment in 1892 at Elisavetgrad's Gustav Neuhaus School of Music.³

Early studies were primarily focused on piano until the school quickly noticed his potential to be a composer. At the school, he was also introduced to German classical compositions and

composers among Alexander Scriabin and Frederic Chopin.⁴ In 1900, he began writing his first piano poems without any master guidance or serious schooling, and his Opus 1 contained nine short piano preludes (1900-1902).⁵ Szymanowski later attended the Warsaw State Conservatory in 1901; during this time, he studied especially under Zygmunt Noskowski (1846-1909) – a famous composer, conductor, journalist, and one of the most famous teachers who taught virtually all other important composers of the following generation.⁶ After his studies from 1903 to 1905 under Noskowski, Szymanowski moved to Berlin, where he founded the Young Polish Composers' Publishing Company, which aimed to publish new works by other Polish composers, along with the "Young Poland in Music" Society.⁷ These years were primarily spent absorbing and studying the musical language of later German master composers, particularly Richard Strauss, with the resulting influence leading to the production of his first two symphonies in 1907 and 1909.⁸

During the years leading up to World War I, Szymanowski traveled extensively throughout Europe to broadcast and publicize his name as a composer, along with fellow Poles, including violinist Paul Kochansky and Arthur Rubinstein, and uphold the newest artistic trends in Europe.⁹ Surrounded by his fellow countrymen, he composed numerous piano pieces, including preludes, etudes, and variations (1901-1905), which Rubinstein introduced in his concerts, and a sonata and Notturmo e Tarantella (1909-1914) both for violin – which Kochanski had introduced.¹⁰ In 1908, he returned to his hometown, later spending the years 1912 to 1914 in Vienna before briefly staying in Paris the same year, which cemented his admiration for Claude Debussy and the French school of Impressionism.¹¹

Later Life

The years during the war were spent at his family's estate in Timoshovka – wherein he composed extensively, including his third symphony, first violin concerto, and first string quartet.

During these years up to 1917, he also studied ancient Greek drama, Islamic culture, and philosophy.¹² Britannica notes Szymanowski's musical shift resulting from these studies:

Szymanowski's works from this period, which include *Mity* (1914; "Myths"), *Metopy* (1915; "Metopes"), and *Maski* (1916; "Masques"), show great originality and diversity of style. He softened his dynamic extremes, employed coloristic orchestration, and used polytonal and atonal material while retaining the expressive melodic style of his earlier works. With the establishment of an independent Polish state in 1918, [he] became deeply interested in the Polish folk idiom and tried to create a Polish national style, a task unattempted since Chopin. He also became more conservative, abandoning his atonal vocabulary. Living in Zakopane [a city in south-central Poland near the Slovakian border], the regional centre of the Tatra mountain people [(the Carpathian Mountains)], he adopted their tonal language, syncopated rhythms, and winding melodies in his new style.¹³

Timoshovka endured heavy suffering during Russia's Bolshevik Revolution in 1917, leading to Szymanowski and his family relocating to Elisavetgrad, only before the city became occupied by Austria, where in 1919, the family was forced to sell all the family land at a heavy loss.¹⁴ Szymanowski soon found a new home in Poland's capital city of Warsaw in 1920, where, after achieving some success, he eventually became the director of the Warsaw Conservatory in 1926. During the 1920s, his compositions became known to a broader audience as a result of their inclusion in the annual programs that the International Society of Contemporary Music had sponsored, leading to his emergence as Poland's most prominent composer – this is primarily the result of his wide travels, as he promoted his works himself throughout Paris, London, and the United States, among various other locations throughout Europe.¹⁵

At the time of his work at the Warsaw Conservatory, his compositions turned to reflect his Polish heritage – including a ballet-opera in 1926 based on Polish peasant traditions and music (*Harnasie*), his *Stabat Mater* for solo voices, orchestra, and mixed chorus in 1928 which recalls counterpoint in the style of Palestrina with Slavic melodies, and a 12 song cycle written in 1930 which had been inspired by the folk music of Poland's Kurpie Region. Also notable are his second violin concerto, written in 1930, and his *Symphonie Concertante* for orchestra and piano in 1932,

both of which feature a distinctly Polish nature.¹⁶ In 1928, Szymanowski became seriously ill and lost his position at the conservatory temporarily, being diagnosed with an acute form of tuberculosis.¹⁷

End of Life

Szymanowski traveled to Davos, Switzerland, in 1929 for medical treatment, later resuming his position in 1930 after his time abroad.¹⁸ The school, however, had been closed two years later under a legislative decision – the result of which led to his move to Villa Atma in Zakopane, where he eagerly composed and immersed himself further into the Polish folk idiom and the culture of the Gorals (Polish Highlanders) of which he enveloped their winding melodic styles, syncopated rhythms, and tonal language into his new musical style.¹⁹

In the last few years of Szymanowski's life, because of his deteriorating finances, he was forced to make numerous business trips and perform publicly, though he always mocked his ability to play the piano. He wrote his fourth symphony specifically for this purpose and performed it as a piano concert soloist.²⁰ Not long after, his health conditions worsened – he left Zakopane permanently in 1935 and traveled to Grasse, France, the following year to receive additional treatment at a sanatorium for his tuberculosis.²¹ This proved to no longer be effective, and the following year, he traveled to Lausanne, Switzerland, where he passed away at the capital city's sanatorium on March 29, 1937.²² Stanisława Szymanowska (Karol's sister) brought his body back to Poland where he was laid to rest at Skalka (Church of St. Michael the Archangel and St. Stanislaus the Bishop and Martyr Basilica), in Kraków, Poland – a local church and monastery known particularly as a “national Panthéon” for highly distinguished Poles.²³ He has since been honored in numerous commemorations, as noted by the National Bank of Poland:

On [November 16th, 2006], the Polish Parliament passed a resolution to name 2007 “The Year of Karol Szymanowski” in order to honor the 125th anniversary of the composer's

birth and the 70th anniversary of his death. On [October 3rd, 2007], the National Bank of Poland issued special commemorative coins depicting the composer in the following denominations: 200 zloty, 10 zloty and 2 zloty. The Karol Szymanowski Academy of Music in Katowice [(A city in southern Poland)] as well as the Kraków Philharmonic have been both named in remembrance of the composer. On [November 11th, 2018], to commemorate the 100th anniversary of the regaining of Polish independence, President Andrzej Duda posthumously awarded Szymanowski [among] 24 other distinguished Poles, Poland's highest decoration the Order of the White Eagle.²⁴

Among this, he received a multitude of other significant awards, including the Officer and Commander of the Order of the Crown of Italy, the Officer Cross and Commander Cross of Polonia Restituta, the Knight of Legion d'Honneur, and many others, including an honorary doctorate of Kraków's Jagiellonian University as well as numerous honorary memberships of various conservatories and academies across Europe.²⁵

Compositions

Szymanowski is most known for his orchestral works – four symphonies, two violin concertos, string quartets, Stabat Mater, and numerous other orchestral songs, including many with voice. Beyond this, he wrote a large number of piano music, including his four etudes, multiple mazurkas, and metopes (a miniature tone poem drawing on Greek mythology), as well as various accompanying pieces such as sonatas, nocturnes, and other tone poems for violin and piano among other chamber compositions.²⁶ He also transcribed numerous past composers' works, such as 3 Paganini Caprices arranged for violin and piano.²⁷ Samson notes, "Szymanowski adopted no thorough-going alternatives to tonal organization [...] the harmonic tensions and relaxations and the melodic phraseology have clear origins in tonal procedure, but [...] an underpinning tonal framework has been almost or completely dissolved away."²⁸

Outside of orchestral compositions, Szymanowski composed numerous stage works and vocal repertoire. His ballets *Harnasie* and *Mandragora* were well received during his time, among his operas *Hagith* and *King Roger*, which were regarded as his masterpieces.²⁹ Lesser known but

equally important are his selections of vocal works, including his multiple “songs” opuses (which include many cultural works) and choral repertoires such as his well-known *Stabat Mater* and “6 Kurpian Songs.”³⁰ Szymanowski left behind over 250 works, including some that had been lost, as well as a two-volume novel (whose manuscript was lost in a fire during the siege of Warsaw, September 1939) entitled “*Efebos*,” based on the subject of homosexuality and a reflection of Szymanowski’s personal identity and experiences during his travels – especially those to the Mediterranean area.³¹ A central chapter and notation written by Szymanowski notes that the novel depicts “the history of a gradual liberation from various types of traditional, inherited slavery by an increasingly clear mirage of true freedom of the soul.”³²

Influence

Although much like Frederic Chopin, Szymanowski’s life was cut short – the resulting magnitude of recognition he received, however, proved to be limitless. Benjamin Schultz describes the cultural influence passed on by the composer:

Nonetheless, Karol Szymanowski [...] is widely considered to be the key composer in making the transition of Polish music from the 19th century to a truly significant 20th-century Polish style. A writer of songs (with orchestra and piano), choral music, and opera [...] and other stage works, he was the first composer after Chopin to achieve a worldwide reputation. Strongly motivated by Chopin’s attainment of an internationally recognized “Polish style,” his highly innovative writing successively spanned romanticism that reflected Chopin, Scriabin, Reger, Richard Strauss, and others, an impressionistic style blended with diverse eclectic influences and another that was folk-based. [Szymanowski] also influenced many young Polish composers to study in Paris, where they could study different stylistic trends.³³

Not only did his musical proficiency and diverse compositional styles leave a mark on the music around him, but his devotion to music and varied education left a shockwave across new composers, especially young Poles, to whom he dedicated the bulk of his work. Karol Szymanowski was both a musical leader and icon in his lifetime, and his remaining vestige proved his devotion to his country and a lasting inspiration to its people.

Notes

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